

AN ENERGY AUDIT OF PURPOSE-BUILT GOVERNMENT HOUSING UNITS IN NIGERIA

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ABSTRACT

The electricity use characteristics of 16 air conditioned houses each of 2 bedrooms flat government owned housing unit in Gusau, Nigeria were investigated. Monthly electricity consumption data were gathered and analysed to obtain a breakdown of the energy use. Results show an annual electricity consumption of 572933 kWh with energy use per unit gross floor area of 236.73 kWh/m². The percentage consumption for the three major electricity end users, namely air conditioning, electrical appliances and lighting were 78%, 21%, and 1%, respectively. Suggestions made to reduce energy consumption include the use of 1.13kW (1.5hp) air conditioners, fluorescent or sodium lamps, ballasts, motion sensors, natural ventilation and solar energy.

KEY WORD: Housing units; Energy use characteristics; Energy utilization

INTRODUCTION

High energy consumption is one of the serious problems in the world today. Recently, this question has taken on not only economic, but also ecological and social importance. The most important environmental issue is CO emissions. In the future, the external costs of the environment will be included in the price of energy and energy efficient buildings will be very important. Energy audits are one of the most useful tools for increasing the energy efficiency in European countries (Butala and Novak, 1999).

In the United States on the other hand, buildings consume a significant portion of energy. Buildings consume nearly half of all the energy in the country for heating, cooling, and power, and it is estimated that nearly 30% of this consumption could be saved by energy conservation and/or sustainable building design and operations (Clarke, 1993). According to other sources, more than 50% of all delivered energy in Europe and the United States can be associated with buildings. In the United Kingdom for example, more than 60% of energy is used to condition the indoor environment (Tham, 1993). Energy efficiency of air-conditioning systems is clearly of global importance. Studies have shown that in South Africa, approximately 20% of all available municipal electrical energy is used in commercial and office buildings. Further studies have shown that air conditioning is responsible for a substantial share of energy use (50%) (Mathews *et al.*, 2001). Efforts to improve energy efficiency should therefore not only concentrate on the design of the air-conditioning system but also include the building itself.

Lahti Declaration (Husu, 2006) on the promotion of energy efficiency and renewable energy through energy auditing which was made by representatives from 39 countries and 8 international organisations, having met at the International Energy Audit Conference in Lahti, Finland. 11th – 13th September, 2006, is committed to intensify their work to promote energy efficiency and the use of renewable energy in their countries and organisations.

Among many statements declared:

1. They underline that energy auditing procedures, where specialists systematically analyse the energy use of buildings and production processes and make proposals for cost-effective energy efficiency improvements, are key methods in finding the most effective measures to improve energy efficiency. The promotion of the use of renewable energy sources can and should also be a natural part of energy auditing.
2. They encourage governments, in cooperation with the private sector, to create and further develop their own energy audit programmes or activities as part of their energy efficiency programmes, and in so doing to make effective use of international experiences and best practices. They should be complemented by

awareness raising campaigns, targeting energy users. In addition self-auditing tools should be developed and made available for energy consumers.

In Nigeria, energy auditing is not a wide spread practice, despite Nigeria through the Energy Commission of Nigeria has policy to that effect (Sambo, 2007).

Table 1. Physical characteristics of the housing unit buildings

Component	Description
Wall	200mm concrete 10mm mortar plaster insulation Inside and outside layers U-value $\frac{1}{4}$ 0.36W/m ² k Total wall area=50.42 m ² for each room
Roof	200mm Asbestos sheet 50mm ceiling board insulation U-value $\frac{1}{4}$ 0.36W/m ² k
Glazing	Single glass, transparent
People (number of people)	5-11
Lighting in each house	10,100W bulbs
Appliances in each house	Video/Television (1); Pressing electric iron(1); A/C (3) and Fridge (2)

In light of the foregoing, an energy audit for some housing units in Gusau has been conducted. Gusau the economic state capital of Zamfara State in the northern part of the country. It receives ample sustainable amount of rainfall throughout the year. Its climatic condition is influenced by the dry and dust harmatan. The rainfall covers up to 5-6 months while the remaining months are dry season (Umar, 2001). This hot and humid climatic area is characterized by a high incidence of thermal discomfort due to warmth for most of the year. To overcome such situation, government initiated some purposed built environment housing unit to achieve bio-climatic comfort. During this hot period, a considerable proportion of domestic energy consumption is used to achieve bio-climatic comfort. This proportion is quite significant in overall energy use and the cost to the state economy is consequently very high (Umar, 2001). Thus there is the need for effective utilisation and management of energy. This is the aim of this study through the following objectives:

To survey and analyse the energy consumption pattern for the housing unit and establish energy saving schemes for the housing unit.

MATERIAL AND METHOD

Description of the housing unit.

The housing unit is situated at the eastern part of Gusau central at latitude 12.10⁰N, longitude 6.42⁰E and occupies a land area of 150 metres square which is fenced with a cement block wall enclosing 16 houses each of 2 bedrooms flat. Each house has 3 Air conditioners, three 100 watts bulb in each bedroom, four 100 watts bulb in the sitting room and various house hold electrical equipments. Inventories of all the electrical appliances installed in the housing unit and a summary of the key building data and information on the building envelope designs are presented in Table 1.

Energy Audit.

The study examined the energy consumption pattern for the various energy outlets (lighting, air conditioners, fridge and household Appliances). Some field assistants were used to collect energy consumption data, fill out questionnaire for analysis and measure the internal dimension of the housing unit. Data for the occupants total energy consumption was obtained from monthly electricity consumption cards for each building. In order to assess the energy consumption of the light alone the light were put on and the energy consumed from the electric meter was recorded. The same was done for the fridge alone, air conditioners and other electrical appliances.

Changes were then proposed to make energy use more efficient in order to save energy. Among measures include the use of day light as substitute to artificial light in the building, so that the energy consumed by the air conditioners is reduced drastically. Economics analyses were also carried out where feasible to know whether the cost of the changes and the cost of the extra load if not tempered with are worth doing.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION.

The results of the energy analysis carried out and the recommended or suggested practices to conserve energy are presented.

Table 2 presents the annual energy consumption pattern of the housing units. The table shows that the total annual energy consumption is 572933.5 kWh of which the air conditioners consume 77.6 percent while electrical appliances and lightings consumed 21.2 and 1.2 percent respectively. Due to the high temperatures and the arid conditions, the air conditioners had to consume a lot of energy to condition the rooms to comfortable levels. The air conditioners were the main cooling systems. No electric fans were installed in the housing units. Most of the 48 air conditioners installed are the 2 hp rating. They are designed to operate at 32 °C ambient temperature but investigation reveals they operate at 35 –37 °C ambient temperature for most of the time when in use. Table 3 presents the power demand and energy consumption of domestic appliances. It shows that electric pressing iron consumes the highest (56.81%) while video consumes the least, which is (0.59%). The ratings of the fridges are 220 watts and 25 in numbers. Energy consumed could be saved by 13.64 percent, if these fridges are replaced with the ones with 190 watts ratings. Values of the cooling load computed for the houses are presented in Table 4. The table shows the heat load gained from the various items. These are the loads that must be overcome before the room is cooled. The ability to reduce these heat gains will lead to energy savings, as the air conditioners will expend lesser energy to cool the rooms. These savings are presented in column 3 of Table 4.

TABLE 2 Annual electricity use by the energy end users.

Energy end users	Consumption (kWh)	Percentage of the total (%)	Energy used index (kWh/m ²)
Air Conditioner	444342.91	77.55	183.60
Lightings	7008.00	1.22	2.90
Appliances	121582.59	21.23	50.24
Total	572933.50	100.00	236.73

ENERGY SAVING OPPORTUNITIES IN THE HOUSING UNIT.

Based on the evaluation of energy use pattern of the houses, several energy conservation measures (ECM) were analyzed. Energy conservation measures were classified into the three categories of no cost, low cost and major cost investment measures as discussed below.

No-cost measures.

These are measures that can be implemented through operational and behavioural means without the need for system or building alterations and, therefore, do not require extra cost for their implementation (Lam *et al.*, 2004). For the housing units, the following measures were identified for implementation.

ECM # 1: Schedule of air conditioning and lighting.

The turning off the A. C. system during early hours of the morning (from 6 am to 8 am) will lead to a considerable reduction of 15 percent of total annual energy used and energy cost saving of 566,000 naira.

ECM # 2: set point temperature

In this ECM, the impact of indoor temperature setting on energy use is analyzed. The cooling temperature should be set at 25⁰C for the hot season months and at 22⁰C for other months compared to the base case set point temperatures of 24⁰C for the hot season months and 20⁰C for other months. This ECM will result in annual reduction in energy consumption of 3% from analysis carried out using DOE 4 software.

ECM # 3: infiltration

In this ECM, the impact of indoor air infiltration on energy use is analyzed. Sometimes a door may be left open while A. C. system is working, this would cause large amount of energy waste and this simple action alone can undoubtedly incur enormous “invisible” expenditure in electricity bill for such a single action.

Table 3. Annual energy distribution for energy consumed by the electrical appliances

Item	Consumption (kWh)	Percent of the total consumption (%)
Video	711.58	0.59
Television	4088.00	3.40
Fridge	47664.00	39.20
Iron	69120.00	56.81
Total	121583.58	100.00

Low-cost measures

These are measures that can be implemented for building alterations or modifications and thus, extra but low cost is required for their implementation.

ECM # 4: Energy-efficient lamps

There are a variety of simple and inexpensive measures to improve the efficiency of lighting systems. These measures include the use of energy-efficient lighting lamps and ballasts, the addition of reflective devices and delamping. For the housing units under study, the use of 100W bulbs meets more than the required illumination. The 100w bulb should be replaced with 60W bulbs or 40W fluorescent. If this is done it will lead to 16 percent reduction in the energy consumed. Also the use of photocells or sensors should be installed in some rooms with low occupancy with the view of reducing energy consumption. One method of reducing the lighting energy is to the use of day lighting and this should be put in place.

ECM # 5: Passive cooling measure:

These practices tend to diminish the thermal constraint and also reduce to a minimum the gains from outside. Walls must be protected from the sun, either by roof, running over or by trees placed at 2 or 3m from the wall. Insulation of building walls can help but not to a large extent due to the small variation of the atmospheric temperature in Gusau. Natural ventilation may be used for parts of the mornings when the weather may be cool. This method is effective for buildings, which are surrounded with shade trees. It was found that shade trees could reduce energy consumption of the air conditioners by as much as 15% to 20%. Air conditioners may be combined with the use of ceiling fans to cut down energy consumption. A reduction of up to 10% was found to be possible in this manner.

Major investment measures

These measures require major financial investment for their implementation. They can be implemented through system renovation or retrofitting to the office building or for new similar projects.

ECM # 6: replacement of 1.5 kW (2 hp) AC system with 1.13 kW (1.5 hp) AC system.

As an energy conservation measure, changing the system to a 1.13 kW system reduces the amount of electricity consumed by 370W for each unit and for all the units the reduction will be 17.76kW. On an average, 24.67% reduction in energy consumption is achieved for the hot season months. This ECM can be used more effectively in future similar housing and office buildings.

CONCLUSION

The electrical energy consumption of the housing unit has been successfully surveyed. The consumption is attributed to lighting, air conditioners and household equipment. It was found out that air conditioners accounted for over 77% of the housing energy consumption, equipment accounted for over 21% and lighting for about 1%. Suggestions have been made to reduce energy consumption. These include the use of 1.13kW (1.5hp) air conditioners, fluorescent or sodium lamps, ballasts, motion sensors, natural ventilation and solar energy.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the conclusions of this research work, the following recommendations are made for the existing housing units as well as for similar future projects:

1. It is recommended that the schedule of lighting and equipment should be adjusted so that they are turned off during unoccupied or low occupancy hours.
2. It is recommended to use low-emittance double-glazed windows for energy efficiency especially in large glazed rooms.
3. It is recommended that energy-efficient lamps of fluorescent type having a power of 40W or less are used. However, for existing buildings, these energy saving lamps can be used when existing lamps are burned or fused.
4. The 2 hp air conditioners be phased out and replaced by 1.5hp units provided it is properly shaded with trees. If shade is provided the cooling load would be reduced by 200w thus reducing energy consumption.
5. The refrigerator should be moved from the sitting room to the kitchen or a corridor and if that alone is done, the refrigerator may work more effectively in the corridor since there is enough ventilation and also the air conditioner in the sitting room is saved from working harder to remove the additional heat transfer by the refrigerator. This should be avoided in future projects
6. Regular maintenance cultures should be put in place.

Table 4. Cooling Loads and Proposed Energy Savings

Items	Initial Load (kWh)	Final load after conservation	Savings (kW)
Lights	480,000	192000	288000 (60%)
Fridge	165,000	142500	22800 (13.8)
Walls	1451520	726048	725472 (50%)
Glass	1244160	349920	894240 (71.87%)
Roof	684,000	259,200	388,800 (46.84)
TOTAL			2319310

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